

Play•IT

A Methodology for Designing and Evaluating Educational Play Experiences for Children with Cognitive Disabilities

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Abstract: Play•IT is a design and evaluation methodology for developing and evaluating educational experiences for children with cognitive disabilities such as autism, epilepsy and cerebral palsy to interact as peers with neurologically typical children, caregivers, parents, and teachers. This methodology is a guideline for designing social inclusion technologies based on emotional, social, behavioral, and motivational criteria.

Key words: Cognitive Disabilities, Autism, Experience Design, Design for Children

1. Introduction

A growing number of children and adults are living with cognitive and developmental disabilities such as autism, epilepsy, and cerebral palsy. The CDC defines developmental disabilities as a diverse group of severe chronic conditions that are due to mental and/or physical impairments. Individuals with developmental disabilities have problems with major life activities such as language, mobility, learning, self-help, and independent living. The CDC also says that learning how people with developmental disabilities can improve the quality of their lives is one of the CDC's main goals for these individuals [1]. In addition, some neurological and genetic disorders have dramatically increased over the past several decades. According to the Center for Disease Control Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report (MMWR) from December 18, 2009, autism rates are as high as one in 80 in some areas of the U.S., representing a 57% increase in incidence between 2002 and 2006 [2]. And there are many factors involved in providing lifetime care for these individuals, just the financial cost of caring for a child with autism over their lifetime is estimated to be 3.5 million dollars. Therefore, since autism spectrum disorders (ASD) do not typically shorten the lifespan, says autism specialist Dr. Michael Chez, our society needs to prepare for long-term care of these children as they grow to adulthood. Therefore improving early intervention and quality of life, reversing some aspects of these autistic behaviors at a neurological level, and improving social deficits in communication and awareness of others will benefit everyone [3].

This research focuses on a design and evaluation methodology for creating educational experiences that will mediate social interactions between typical children and children with cognitive or developmental disabilities such as autism, epilepsy and cerebral palsy. This methodology emphasizes the critical emotional, social, physical, and language skills needed by this group of children. This methodology for social inclusion information technology (IT), called the Play•IT Model, also addresses the need for designed solutions to consider differences in social, ethical, and physical issues facing the multiple constituent groups. It also takes into consideration the importance of age appropriateness and stylistic appeal to both the child with disabilities and to the typical peers.

This model emphasizes that designed solutions must not be branded or positioned as “disabilities” products. They must have learning outcomes that are beneficial to all constituent groups.

The goals of Play•IT are to incorporate multi-sensory data into a design solution, explore information design and usability as they apply to learning new information for persons with cognitive disabilities, create visually dynamic design solutions, and incorporating learning strategies.

2. Design and Evaluation Methodology

The Play•IT design and evaluation methodology is based on three components; the mental trilogy, activity theory, and the Connectivity Model. It also adds ethnographic research strategies from information architecture and educational techniques from Dewey and Vygotsky that are specifically designed to understand and work with the idiosyncratic nature of cognitive and developmental disabilities. It then uses the physical and psychological information about the disabilities to inform the design decision-making process in a way that minimizes the impact of the disability on the experience and maximizes the child’s strengths. These research strategies are then combined with information design theories to create a comprehensive design and evaluation methodology that serves as a socially mediating educational experience between multiple target audiences.

2.1 Trilogy of the Mind

Throughout history the mind has been viewed as a tripartite amalgam that includes cognition, emotion, and motivation. It is important to understand not only how we attend to, remember, or reason, but also why we do these things. Thinking, says LeDoux, cannot be fully comprehended if emotions and motivations are ignored. Human brains have two specialized systems for memory, one verbal and one nonverbal. The verbal system is based on speech comprehension. However, many children with cognitive and developmental disabilities have speech impairment. Therefore the second, non-verbal memory system is very important in terms of its ability to communicate to these children and capitalize on the more functional parts of their brains. The nonverbal member systems are epitomized by the sensory systems that are triggered by unique stimuli such as sights, sounds, smell, and tactile sensations [4].

2.2 Activity Theory

Activity Theory is based on the work of Lev Vygotsky. Vygotsky argued that there was a unity between perception, speech and action. He also emphasized the importance of mediating devices such as symbols, tools, artifacts, or environments in the development of mind and thought. Figure 1 shows Engeström’s model of activity theory based on the relationship between people, artifacts, objects or motives, and society [5].

Figure 1. Engeström's model of activity theory

Activity theory is an effective model for the design and evaluation of Play•IT experiences because it is based on the idea that humans develop and learn when they collaborate with other people in their society as mediated by an instrument in their immediate surroundings. It is also appropriate from the standpoint that a designed instrument can facilitate learning and social interactions based on motivation.

2.3 Connectivity Model

Connectivity model is a method that uses audience analysis to understand the characteristics of a target audience, with regard to their activities, emotions, motivations, and cognition. Experience design considers the artifact or environment being designed as part of a larger experience. It considers the social and emotional needs of the user, as well as the physical constraints of the project. Only those design solutions that meet these requirements will be considered optimal solutions (Figure 2). In addition, any well formed project description that considers the social, emotional, and physical constraints will have a plethora of optimal solutions [6].

Figure 2. optimal solution zone based on the intersection of physical constraints and spheres of socially and emotionally appropriate experiences

The Connectivity Model, Figure 3, has been developed for this research to bridge the gap between *Kansei* assessment and Activity Theory. It integrates the basic relationships of activity theory and combines them with

the emotional and social aspects of *Kansei* assessment. This model contextualizes usability in terms of its social and emotional appropriateness as well as its physical and cultural context [7].

Figure 3. connectivity model and its relationship to activity theory

2.4 Information Architecture

A three circle methodological diagram for information architecture as seen in Figure 4 can be used to describe the relationship of context, content, and users when designing Play•IT experiences [8]. The Play•IT experience is designed to fall in the intersection point between the context, content, and the users. It also important to acknowledges that for the Play•It experiences there are multiple users with varying abilities to access content, thus educational techniques such as scaffolding and scalability must be built into the learning process. The content for Play•IT experiences should be educational and have a variety of appropriate levels of learning. It should be designed in a way that various audiences can access the information that they are most interested in without being distracted by information that is not specifically targeted to them. This can be done through visual and sensory design strategies that break up or categorize information and communicate it through different verbal or nonverbal channels.

Figure 4. information architecture circles of influence

3. Analyzing Cognitive Disabilities

Often sensory toys or games are inappropriate to the social and emotional needs of the target audience. In order to design experiences that are appropriate for children with cognitive disabilities the nature of those disabilities must be thoroughly understood (Figure 5).

Figure 5 a twelve-year-old-child in a typical physical therapy session using a sensory toy that is inappropriate to his chronological age. Photo by D. Satterfield.

It is important to understand the fundamental characteristics of cognitive and physical disabilities such as autism, epilepsy, and cerebral palsy when designing and developing social inclusion technologies. Each condition affects the child in very idiosyncratic ways. This makes it important to understand what the variability is in the areas of social, emotional, physical, motivational, and behavioral realms. Play•IT examines the physical and psychological aspects of a disability and uses that information to determine what impact the disability will have on each part of the designed experience. For example, children with autism, epilepsy and cerebral palsy are all prone to seizures. However, the child with autism may only experience an occasional seizure while the child with CP or epilepsy is often time much more dramatically affected by them. In addition, some seizures affect physical abilities such as motor control or speech, while others may only impact memory. Information about these physical conditions should be used to determine how to design the content and interactions of a Play•IT experience to minimize the physical aspects of the disability and maximize the quality of the learning experience.

3.1 Audience Analysis and Ethnographic Research

The observation of children with cognitive and developmental disabilities is critical to understanding their reactions and behaviors as they apply to social and emotional interactions. Because children with cognitive disabilities are very idiosyncratic in their abilities, it is important to compare the observations of children with cognitive impairments to those of typical peers. This comparison also allows the designer to use typical peer

interests and interactions as a benchmark for designs. When paired with other forms of ethnographic research, direct observation allows the information to be properly contextualized. For example, without direct observation it is hard to envision how the gait of an autistic child varies from that of a child with epilepsy, cerebral palsy, or from that of a typical child. Observations must include an account of physical characteristics, eye contact, sensory awareness, emotional states, socialization, cognitive abilities, motivations, distractions, and events that trigger inappropriate self-stimulator (stims) behaviors. Because cognitive, physical, social, and emotional issues vary greatly between children, it is important to observe a wide variety of kids and situations.

Interviews with caregivers, teachers and aides are also recommended. Teachers and one-on-one student aides can give useful information about the classroom. It is important that the Play•IT instruments be appropriate to the physical conditions of the school environment. This might include things such as being easy to carry between classrooms, meeting sound requirements that allow the child to hear but do not disrupt the classroom, have a battery life that is longer than the typical school day, and has a screen that adapts to a variety of lighting conditions. Andyland is an example of a game with flexible play considerations designed for children with ASD to gain language and socially rehearse communication skills (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Andyland, a game for children with ASD, teaches communication skills at home or in a classroom

Peer mentors and friends of the children are also important sources of information. Peers give information about the social and emotional expectations of the child's community. The designed Play•IT experience must meet the social, emotional, and stylistic expectations of the typical peers. If the device is inherently motivating to a typical peer then acceptance of the experience will be greater and it will be effective in creating a positive social experience. Parent and sibling interviews are important for designs that will be used in the home.

3.2 Physical Disabilities

According to Grandin and Barron, we have to look at the physical biomedical/biochemical underpinnings of children with disabilities such as autism, assess their sensory issues, determine whether they think from a logical or emotional framework, and then create educational experiences that take into consideration all of these factors.

[9]” As a method of assessment, these physical disabilities can be categorized according to the sensory systems that they impact. By thinking of physical disabilities in this way, designs can make sure that they have appropriate multi-modal communication channels. By repeating auditory information as text in a visual channel, it can accommodate both the disabilities of sight and hearing. However, it can also serve as a cue or scaffolding strategy for a child with a reading disability or a cognitive deficit in that area. Physical expectations should be challenging but not impossible for the child to accomplish. It should also be noted that an accurate assessment of physical capabilities is more relevant than any particular diagnosis with regard to designing Play•IT experiences.

4. Therapeutic Benefits

Many children with physical disabilities spend hours a week in therapies to build skills and remediate deficiencies. These therapies are often very repetitive and boring. In addition, many of the physical disabilities are due to brain injuries, so progress is extremely slow and greatly taxes the child’s endurance. In addition, many of the children have no idea why they are being put through these rigors and have no real motivation to do the therapies. Therefore, any designed experience that can incorporate therapeutic benefits within the context of a fun or motivational experience should be considered. Typical therapy areas included speech therapy that addresses expressive and receptive language disabilities, occupational therapy that mainly involves fine motor and dexterity issues, physical therapy that addresses balance and body awareness issues, and group therapies that generally address social awareness and emotional reciprocity. In addition, therapeutic benefits can be incorporated into Play•IT experiences without being the express purpose of the activity. If the therapeutic benefit is the purpose of the activity then it should be designed in conjunction with professional therapists. (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Sign•a•Long, a game for ASD children, helps them to acquire language and physical imitation skills

4.1 Sensory Issues

When sensory issues are distorted, the child's true potential will never be discovered. The child will always be seen as incapable, when all of the child's energy is spent trying to deal with the invasive overstimulation of information in the environment. [10]" For children with cognitive disabilities, the environment has a direct relationship to their behavior. A loud or chaotic sensory setting can lead to disruptive or negative behaviors, while a tranquil sensory environment can have a calming effect on a child with cognitive disabilities [11]. Therefore setting up a positive learning environment by carefully controlling sensory elements will create a more effective Play•IT experience.

When designing Play•IT experiences sensory integration should be considered. Sensory modulation and desensitization should be incorporated through tailorable interfaces that allow for elements to be controlled and increased as the child becomes more able to handle them. A sensory diet should be included that deliberately incorporates a variety of sensory elements. These sensory elements can also often be used to enhance the communication aspects of the experience in terms of multi-modality. Because sensory rich learning environments are often only found in toys or interfaces designed for young children, these sensory channels are often missing for older children with disabilities even though they still benefit greatly from these experiences. An example of a age appropriate sensory rich learning experience is the WAND navigation device for adolescents with ASD (Figure 8).

Figure 8 WAND, a GPS navigation system for children with ASD, allows them to increase independence levels in their home, school, and neighborhood environments

5. TEACHING STRATEGIES

Sensory information is not limited to therapy. According to John Dewey the sensory system not only takes in information but it also connects with the behavior responses of a child. Says Dewey, "The senses were supposed to be the inlets, the avenues, the gateways, of knowledge, or at least of the raw materials of knowledge. It was not known that the sense-organs are simply the pathways of stimuli to motor-responses, and that it is only through these motor-responses and especially through consideration of the adapting of sense-stimulus and motor-response to each other that growth of knowledge occurs. The sense-qualities of color, sound, contact, etc.

are important not in their mere reception and storage, but in their connection with the various forms of behavior that secure intelligent control. [12]”

Dewey also addresses the important role of motivation that must be incorporated into Play•IT experiences for both children with cognitive disabilities and their neurologically typical peers. Says Dewey, “If we can discover a child’s urgent needs and powers, and if we can supply an environment of materials, appliances, and resources—physical, social, and intellectual—to direct their adequate operation, we shall not have to think about interest. It will take care of itself. For mind will have met with what it needs in order to be mind. [13]”

The customization of Play•IT experiences is also important according to Dewey. He notes that the capacities and needs of a particular set of individuals must be understood. The subject matter or content of educational experiences must also satisfy these needs of the child. Dewey recommends that the learning experiences be flexible enough to permit free play and yet structured enough to give direction towards continuous development of empowerment [14].

5.1 Lessons from Vygotsky

Vygotsky says that the education of children with disabilities acknowledges that along with a deficit often comes combative psychological tendencies and the potential for overcoming the deficit. Education of children with disabilities should take into account those compensation strategies. However, leveraging the capacity of these compensation strategies does not alleviate all of the difficulties raised by the disability. Says Vygotsky, “It means instead concentrating all strengths on the compensation of the defect, and then selecting, in the appropriate sequential order, those tasks which will bring about the gradual formation of the entire personality from a new standpoint. [15]”

5.2 Learning Theory

“Some of these children (formerly labeled as “mentally retarded”) have had superior minds but the sensory pathways have impaired perception in such a way as to disturb their learning. In such cases it is necessary to understand the nature of the disturbances and to develop a remedial teaching program to compensate for them. Because visual, auditory, tactile, and kinesthetic imagery are essential to most learning, the sensory paths of these sense modes are examined briefly here. [16]”

“All these somesthetic functions are intimately involved with all learning that requires tactile sensitivity or kinesthetic awareness of body image, body movement, or manual recognition of three-dimensional forms...In the classroom these skills include arithmetic, writing, spelling, and reading... For this reason, calisthenics, the trampoline and other techniques to exercise large body movements have been said to be related to improvement in reading and other academic subjects. [17]”

5.3 Behaviorism

Behaviorism and the research of Ivar Lovaas has produced numerous studies showing the efficacy of Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) in making gains in language, social, self-help, and play skills [18]. The training is based on the concept that skills are broken down into discrete steps that can be taught in a building process

through repetition and reinforcement of correct responses. The discrete trial training process is well suited to HCI solutions because the computer can be used to do drill and practice situations very easily.

5.4 Reinforcement

Reinforcement is the use of rewards to praise efforts in line with desired actions. The use of reinforcement is considered necessary for changing behaviors. However in order to be most effective, it must be determined what is reinforcing to a particular person at a particular time. This is done through a process of negotiation for reinforcement. In Play•IT this is done through offering a variety of possible reinforcements that can be chosen by the target audience. In addition, there should be a scalability of those reinforcers. This is known as differential reinforcement. This allows for better or more desirable reinforcers for more accurate responses. By using differential reinforcement, target behaviors or desired responses are achieved more quickly. In addition, a reinforcement strategy borrowed from Errorless ABA is used that reinforces quickly and uses prompting to avoid incorrect responses. This errorless method is effective in avoiding confusion for children with cognitive disabilities by not allowing them to make incorrect selections thus confusing what the correct response looks like. Then when a child is able to correctly respond to a Play•IT situation, the reinforcements are quickly faded and then finally removed [19].

6. PLAY•IT PROJECT DESIGN

In implementing the concepts of ABA into Play•IT design, there must be a task analysis phase. This is where the cognitive content of the play experience must be broken down into smaller discrete trials or tasks that can be reinforced. The reinforcement of these smaller units will quickly allow the child to learn the task and build towards larger goals. It is also important that there is a fade back of prompting in order for the child to gain independent mastery of the targeted skills.

There must also be a material analysis phase in the Play•IT design. This is where the actual physical tasks must be assessed with regard to a child's ability to successfully meet the expectations of the experience in a physical or material sense. In some cases multiple forms of input or task completion should be implemented. For instance, a fine motor task should be paired with a gross motor equivalent or a completely different sensory channel such as an auditory input system so that the child has many options for giving a correct response. This is necessary because for children with cognitive and physical disabilities, a physical inability to respond appropriately is often misinterpreted as a cognitive deficit. This is extremely detrimental to both the child's motivation and learning.

All play experiences should be evaluated with regard to their social and emotional appropriateness. This is important for the self-esteem and empowerment of children with cognitive disabilities. To overcome the stigma associated with these medical conditions, it is extremely important to never give the impression that the child with a cognitive disability is less capable or less important than typical peers. In addition, if the Play•IT experience is not considered age appropriate it will give the impression that the child with a disability is less capable and therefore less socially acceptable. By giving children with cognitive disabilities activities that are socially, emotionally, and age appropriately targeted with regard to their neurologically typical peers, the children will be more likely to perceive each others as equals. It is highly important that the visual appearance and styling of the graphics be on par with other popular products targeted to that age group.

6.1 Play•IT as Social Rehearsal

Play•IT experiences should function as socially mediating devices. They should be customizable and scalable to accommodate a variety of disabilities, as well as be appealing and interesting to typical peers. They should facilitate play as a form of social rehearsal and should empower the child with cognitive disabilities by providing a platform of play that allows multiple target audiences to interact as equals.

7. CONCLUSION

Play•IT brings together research from neuroscience, activity theory, Connectivity Model and information architecture to structure a framework for designing and evaluating social, emotional, and cognitive learning experiences. It emphasizes empowerment of persons with cognitive disabilities by meeting their physical and psychological needs. It creates innovative solutions through targeting the social, emotional, motivational and behavioral needs. Play•IT acknowledges the power of design to create mediating tools that allow social interactions and social rehearsal to take place between target audiences in ways that are natural and motivating to all participants. This area of research empowers people with cognitive disabilities by improving their lifetime skills and helps others appreciate their unique gifts and strengths.

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